

Fermat counters

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Fermat knew that any odd prime p is a sum of two squares if and only if $p - 1$ is divisible by $4m$ for some integer m [1].

Now, any result about primes is an open invitation to discover a counter; in the simplest case here, how many primes are there of the form $(1 + k^2)$ for positive increasing k ? For example, up to $n = 10$ there are five such primes, for $k = 1, 2, 4, 6, 10$; the primes are 2, 5, 17, 37, and 101. Except for 2, the rest obey Fermat's result, of course.

So, what about a counter? Let

$$\Phi_1(n) = \#\{\text{primes of the form } p = 1 + k^2, k \leq n\}$$

Numerical experiments in OCTAVE beginning with $n = 1,000$ and increasing up to 20 million – in variable increments, though mostly 10^5 – suggest the surprising estimate

$$\Phi_1(n) \approx n/\pi \log_{10}(n)$$

for sufficiently large n ; here, of course, $\pi = 3.14159265\dots$ The plot below show the error percentage, decreasing to 0.018% for $n = 20$ million; there are 872,119 such primes up to this bound, while the estimate above yielded the rounded count 871,959.

Next is the hunt for the Fermat counter

$$\Phi_2(n) = \#\{\text{primes of the form } p = 1 + 2k^2, k \leq n\}$$

This time there are four primes of this form up to $n = 10$, for $k = 1, 3, 6, 9$; the primes are 3, 19, 73, and 163.

The convergence to a low error percentage was far slower than above, so the search for a counter began at 1 million, increasing by increments of 300,000, up to 50.2 million. The final estimate, though not as elegant, is

$$\Phi_2(n) \approx n/(\pi \log_{10}(n) - 1/\pi)$$

with an error of 0.025%. The plot below charts the error history.

There are 2,103,219 primes of the form $1 + 2k^2$ up to 50.2 million; the estimated counter gives 2,102,691.

Reference

[1] D. A. Cox, *Primes of the form $x^2 + ny^2$* , Wiley, 2013.